

ABSTRACT ²⁰²⁴ BOOK ²⁴

 **19TH YES
MEETING**

PORTO - PORTUGAL

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Adelino Leite Moreira | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Alexandra Matias | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

André Moreira | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

António Costa Ferreira | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

António Taveira Gomes | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Armando Mansilha | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Dulce Madeira | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Fernando Friões | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Elisa Keating | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Fátima Carneiro | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Francisco Cruz | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Isaura Tavares | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

João Torres | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

José Paulo Andrade | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

João Sérgio Neves | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Luís Delgado | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Manuel Vaz da Silva | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Maria Amélia Ferreira | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Raquel Soares | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Roberto Roncon | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Rui Vaz | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Tiago Taveira Gomes | Faculty of Medicine of the University of Porto

Diagnostic value of the apparent diffusion coefficient in rectal carcinoma

Milica Šarošković¹, Miloš Vuković²

1 - Faculty of Medicine University of Novi Sad; 2- Faculty of Medicine University of Novi Sad, Oncology Institute of
Vojvodina

1. Introduction

The apparent diffusion coefficient (ADC) is a quantitative parameter that facilitates the detection and reliable differentiation of rectal cancer.

2. Aim

MR differentiation between rectal carcinoma, post-radiation proctitis, and normal rectal wall with the ADC values and their correlation with the level of oncological markers and pathohistological characteristics of rectal carcinoma.

3. Methods

MR differentiation between rectal carcinoma, post-radiation proctitis, and normal rectal wall with the ADC values and their correlation with the level of oncological markers and pathohistological characteristics of rectal carcinoma.

4. Results

Mean ADC values of rectal cancer ($0.665 \pm 0.086 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$) were statistically significantly lower than post-radiation proctitis ($1.648 \pm 0.268 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$) and normal rectal wall ($1.180 \pm 0.110 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$) ($p < 0.001$). No difference was found between ADC values in different grades of rectal cancer ($p = 0.874$; $p > 0.05$), depending on the presence of metastases in the lymph nodes ($p = 0.357$; $p > 0.05$), different TN stage ($p = 0.196$; $p > 0.05$), local spread of the tumor ($p = 0.312$; $p > 0.05$), the presence of RAS mutation ($p = 0.829$; $p > 0.05$) and the value of oncological markers ($p = 0.923$; $p > 0.05$). ADC values below $1.013 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$ with 100% sensitivity and 96% specificity indicate the presence of rectal cancer in relation to normal wall, with a positive predictive value of 96.15% and a negative of 100%. ADC values below $1.255 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$ with 100% sensitivity and 95% specificity indicate rectal cancer in relation to post-radiation proctitis. ADC values above $1.339 \times 10^{-3} \text{mm}^2/\text{s}$ with 87% sensitivity and 89% specificity indicate post-radiation proctitis in relation to normal wall, with a positive predictive value of 87.88% and a negative of 87.25%.

5. Discussion/Conclusion

The ADC is a useful marker in differentiating between rectal cancer, post-radiation proctitis and normal rectal wall with high sensitivity and specificity, but it cannot be used to distinguish the histological grades of rectal cancer, nor other pathohistological parameters.